

Assessing Learners' Participation and Challenges in Online Facilitation in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) Institutions in Nigeria

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Abstract

Online facilitation remains a critical component of instructional delivery in single-mode and dual-mode Open and Distance Learning (ODL) institutions across the world. This study focuses on assessing learners' participation and challenges in online facilitation in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) institutions in Nigeria. A Cross-sectional case study survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consists of undergraduate learners from the only single-mode ODL institution in the country (NOUN) and the two oldest dual-mode institutions from Eastern and Southern regions (UNN and DLI, UNILAG) during the 2021/2022 Academic Session. Participants were purposefully selected based on availability and willingness to participate in the study. The total sample size of the study was 829 learners participated in the study. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument used for data collection was; the Students' Participation in Online Facilitation Inventory Scale (SPOFIS) and a reliability coefficient value of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, mean, standard deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The finding reveals that the mean difference in the level of participation in online facilitation across learners' courses of study was found not to be statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Based on the identified challenges, it is, therefore, recommended that ODL institutions should endeavor to make affordable internet available to learners across courses of study, in order to improve their participation in online facilitation.

Keywords: Learner, online facilitation, Participation, Open and Distance Learning

Introduction

Education is seen as a major tool that ensures training of mind for the progress of oneself and society. Whether education is formal or informal, it is known to be an agent of socialization that transforms society over the years. Education occupies a strategic position in the development of the manpower of a nation. This is the reason why nations all over the world continue to invest heavily on their education sector especially in the 21st century where globalization has increased the rate of competition among nations. The way a country progress has a great influence on the quality of education, and her citizens' educational attainment. No wonder Ozturk (2018) submitted that for any country to achieve sustainable economic development; such a country has to invest significantly in her human capital. Education is the strength and wall of any nation's defence and it is well-known fact that no nation rises above the level of its education (Kingdom & Maekae, 2013). A country is termed to be developed when it is able to make qualitative life available to her populace such as social amenities, quality education, infrastructures, and medical care among others.

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) has become a universally recognized form of education which is an essential part of higher education. ODL is an approach which is designed at making education accessible to many people with interest, readiness and willingness to gain exceptionally from quality education which is provided through flexible and affordable distance learning. Open and Distance Learning is a cost-effective instruction that is independent of time, location, pace and space. It can be used for a variety of learning situations, including primary, secondary, tertiary, vocation and non-formal education. It focuses very much on quality assurance, well designed instructional packages, and thrives on exceedingly well-structured and resourced student support (Jegede, 2016). Open and Distance Learning came into existence as a result of universal demand for education, thirst for knowledge and the failure of the conventional education system to cater for the demand for higher education. Open and Distance Learning in recent times has emerged as an alternative to the conventional system, as it has not only proved to be cost effectiveness but also has the potential to reach out to a large segment of the unreached, the marginalized and the needy (Oni, 2019).

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) is practically characterized by the physical separation between tutors and students. This separation reduces the expected level of interaction within the learning space (Bello, 2021). The strategic importance of interaction among students, teachers, and learning content has been well established and referenced in many theories of education, especially constructivism learning theory (Picciano, 2017). The need to bridge the instructional gap that exists between teachers and their learners in open and distance learning (ODL) has been widely acknowledged in literature. Scholars have advocated for instructional delivery channels that will facilitate interaction and engagement in the system particularly during COVID-19 era. Online facilitation remains a crucial component of ODL as it allows seamless interaction between lecturers and students anytime, anywhere.

Online facilitation is the method of promoting learning in an online environment by means of encouraging interaction with and between learners and supporting interactive online learning activities. Online facilitation is an ODL instructional delivery medium that requires knowledgeable personnel with suitable skills and right attitude to moderate teaching-learning process in virtual learning environments. Online facilitation can commonly be seen as the act of managing the learners and learning resources through an online learning platform. Also, online facilitation remains a central element of ODL as it allows continuous interaction between facilitators and learners anytime, anywhere. It has been established that online facilitation strengthens the relationship among the learners and between learners and their tutors (Adesina, 2020).

As the pioneer of single-mode ODL institution in the country, the National Open University of Nigeria remains the magnate in the provision of accessible, credible and affordable learning opportunities at the higher level of education. As part of the effort to stimulate flexible and interactive learning content, the institution recently introduced online facilitation to promote interaction and collaboration among the students and between distance learners and their facilitators. This has been a paradigm shift from the traditional mode of instructional delivery which involved uploading of course materials on the university website for learners to download and read before examinations.

Online facilitation could be carried out in two ways namely: Synchronous and Asynchronous presentations. Synchronous online facilitation has to do with immediate interaction between facilitators and learners using Learning Management Systems (LMSs) like Blackboard, MOODLE and Canvass among other platforms. Then again, asynchronous online facilitation influences the capabilities of discussion tools like chat options with other students. Students may participate in these activities using internet-enabled smart devices i.e. smartphones, tablets, laptops and desktops. Throughout the exercise students are expected to exhibit basic online etiquette. Video conferencing sessions is another asynchronous online facilitation. Here the facilitator will come online for one hour based on a predetermined schedule. The facilitator will briefly explain concepts in a course module or unit under consideration after which he/she answers questions that students may have on the course material. All the video conferencing sessions will be recorded and made available for learners' review and for the benefit of those that could not join the sessions. Lastly on asynchronous, we have an online discussion forum which is a learning tool that gives students a place to express their opinion and understanding regarding the topic outlined for discussion. Learners will be able to challenge one another to think deep on the course while the online facilitator moderates the discussion.

However, this mode of instruction could be hindered by some facilitators-related and learners-related factors. Facilitators have strategic roles to play in content development and delivery. Likewise, effective interaction may be hampered if there is poor participation from learners during online facilitation session. There are a lot of instructional challenges facing online facilitation such as technical problem. No matter how prepared a facilitator is, he or she is bound to face at least a couple of technical problems during most online facilitation sessions. It includes poor audio or video, patchy internet, to background noise in his or her environment. Other challenges can be power failure, unconducive schedule time for online class and lack of good phones or laptop among others. It should also be noted that there are many activities competing for time and resources of

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distance learners ranging from family, work, and social responsibilities. This necessitates the need to examine the level of participation in online facilitation in the face of socio-economic engagements of distance learners. This study therefore focused on assessing the nature of learners' participation and constraints encountered in online facilitation in open and distance learning (ODL) institutions in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the level of students' participation in the following online facilitation related areas;
 - a. accessing and watching of instructional videos;
 - b. attendance and participation at the live classes;
 - c. participation in the discussion form;
 - d. making use of the live chat
2. To investigate perceived challenges hindering effective participation of students in online facilitation at the ODL institutions in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of students' participation in online facilitation as a medium of instructional delivery?
2. What are the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the level of students' participation in online facilitation across the courses of study.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of students' participation in online facilitation across the age groups.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The target population of the study consisted of all undergraduate learners from the only single-mode ODL institution in the country National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) and the two oldest dual-mode institutions from Eastern and Southern regions, University of Nigeria Distance Learning Centre (UNN-DLC), Nsukka and University of Lagos, Distance Learning Institute (UNILAG-DLI), Lagos during the 2021/2022 Academic Session. Participants were purposively selected based on availability and willingness to participate in the study. The total sample size of 829 (Male 423 and Female 406) students participated in the study. Questionnaires were deployed through physical and Google forms to the students of the selected ODL institutions. The instrument used for data collection was the Students' Participation in Online Facilitation Inventory Scale (SPOFIS). The instrument has three sections. Section A deals with students' demography such as: name of the institution, Course of study and age. Section B had 8 items about students' participation in online facilitation activities and Section C had 8 items which contained information on the students' perceived challenges of online facilitation. The reliability coefficient value of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. The draft instrument was subjected to validation process by giving it to Open and Distance Learning experts and practitioners from National Open University of Nigeria and experts in measurement and evaluation at the Faculty of Education of institution. These processes ascertained the face and content validity of the instrument. Data collected for the main study were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the level of students' participation in online facilitation as a medium of instructional delivery?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of learners' participation in online facilitation as a medium of instructional delivery

S/N	Participation in Online Facilitation	SA	A	D	SD	M	STD
1.	Accessing instructional videos;	162(19.6)	196(23.6)	410(49.5)	61(7.4)	2.55	0.884
2.	Watching instructional videos	165(19.9)	208(25.1)	39(48.0)	58(7.0)	2.57	0.882
3.	Attendance at the online live classes	154(18.6)	182(22.0)	405(48.9)	88(10)	2.48	0.911
4.	Participating during the online live classes	145(17.4)	208(25.1)	387(46.7)	89(10.8)	2.48	0.896
5.	Participating in the discussion forum	137(16.5)	159(19.2)	411(49.6)	122(14.7)	2.37	0.923
6.	Making use of the live chat	97(11.7)	133(16.0)	389(46.9)	210(25.3)	2.13	0.917
7.	Responding to email messages	226(27.3)	171(20.6)	301(36.3)	131(15.8)	1.59	1.049
8.	Participating in online quiz	218(26.3)	166(20.0)	283(34.1)	162(19.5)	2.53	1.079

Weighted mean = 2.34 (Low learners' participation in online facilitation)

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Table 2 above showed the level of students' participation in online facilitation as a medium of instructional delivery. More than half of the respondents disagreed that all they participated in the eight online facilitation activities highlighted above. Those that disagreed and strongly disagreed that they participated with each of the eight (8) items are above 50%. Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents they failed to participate in the following facilitation related activities: accessing instructional videos, watching instructional videos, attendance at the online live classes, participating during the online live classes, participating in the discussion forum, making use of the live chat, responding to email messages concerning online facilitation, and participating in online quiz.

Research Question 2

What are the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of learners' challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation

S/N	Challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation of students	SA	A	D	SD	M	STD
1.	Poor internet connectivity	308(37.1)	400(48.3)	94(11.3)	27(3.3)	3.19	0.761
2.	Financial constraints	222(26.8)	334(40.3)	226(27.3)	47(5.7)	2.88	0.867
3.	Official engagements in my work place,	187(22.5)	374(45.1)	207(25.0)	61(7.4)	2.83	0.860
4.	Poor network from the side of the facilitator	195(23.5)	440(53.1)	164(19.8)	30(3.6)	2.96	0.759
5.	Irregular electricity supply	219(26.5)	362(43.7)	203(24.5)	45(5.4)	2.91	0.847
6.	Family responsibilities	133(16.1)	229(27.6)	383(46.2)	84(10.1)	2.49	0.877
7.	Unsuitable time allocation	132(15.9)	342(41.3)	311(37.5)	44(5.3)	2.67	0.801
8.	Lack of access to functional devices	92(11.1)	279(33.7)	368(44.4)	90(10.9)	2.45	0.827

Table 3 above showed the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria. More than half of the respondents agreed that six (6) of the items on the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria are true. Those that agreed and strongly agreed with each of the item on the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the six (6) items on the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria are each above the 2.50 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement in a modified four Likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequency and percentages analyses. Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; the following statements on the challenges hindering effective participation in online facilitation by students in the ODL institutions in Nigeria are true: poor internet connectivity makes it difficult for me to join the online facilitation, financial constraints do hinder me to get data to join online facilitation, official engagements in my work place, often hinder my participation in online facilitation, poor network from the side of the facilitator affects my participation in online facilitation, irregular electricity supply affects my participation in online facilitation and time allocated for online facilitation is always not suitable for me. Meanwhile the following are not true according to the respondents: family responsibilities hinder my participation in online facilitation and access to functional devices affects my participation in online facilitation.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the level of students' participation in online facilitation across the courses of study.

Table 4: ANOVA Table for Comparing students' participation in online facilitation across their courses of study.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	101.467	8	12.683	0.474	0.875ns
Within Groups	21850.528	816	26.778		
Total	21951.995	824			

Ns = Not significant(P>.05)

The F value of 0.474 in table 4 is not statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance, implying that the mean differences in the level of participation in online facilitation across students' course of study are not statistically significant (p > 0.05).

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Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the level of students' participation in online facilitation across their age groups.

Table 5: ANOVA Table for Comparing students' participation in online facilitation across their age groups.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	157.703	3	52.568	1.963	0.115*
Within Groups	21794.733	822	26.514		
Total	21952.436	825			

*=Significance at 0.05

The F value of 1.963 in Table 5 was not statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance, implying that the mean differences in the level of participation in online facilitation across students' age groups are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The differences are therefore not generalisable.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the study revealed that there was low learner participation in online facilitation. This is because more than half of the respondents disagreed that all the eight items such as (accessing instructional videos, watching instructional videos, attendance at online live classes, participating during the online live classes, participating in the discussion forum, making use of the live chat, responding to email messages concerning online facilitation and participating in an online quiz.) on the level of students' participation in online facilitation as a medium of instructional delivery are true. Those that disagreed and strongly disagreed with each of the eight (8) items on the level of students' participation in online facilitation as a medium of instructional delivery were above 50%. This might not be unconnected with the established challenges hindering effective learners' participation in online facilitation in the ODL institutions across Nigeria as indicated in table 3 above. Challenges such as: poor internet connectivity, time allocated for the class, financial constraints, poor network from the side of the facilitator, irregular electricity supply, official engagement in the work place, family responsibilities, and access to functional devices have been established in this study as critical challenges confronting effective participation in online facilitation. Also, epileptic electricity supply weakens most educational activities that rely solely on power supply. This is in line with Idowu (2012) who asserted that no one can meaningfully run ICT – based open and distance learning project without adequate supply of electricity. Therefore, for students to enjoy and participate effectively in online facilitation there must be regular electricity supply. Again, online facilitation is generally an internet-based teaching-learning process, which requires internet services for exchanging ideas and smooth interaction between the facilitators and students. Poor internet connectivity and technical or poor network from the side of the facilitator are some of the challenges faced by students which affect their participation in online facilitation. This result supported the findings of Adesina (2020) that the main challenge to effective online facilitation is poor Internet connectivity which often led to abrupt disconnection from the zoom meetings. Also, the result corroborated Feddy and Dennis (2021) that online teaching is difficult to facilitate sometimes especially if there are technical problems. Resources such as computers, iPhone, stable internet and some others devices are indispensable for online facilitation. Lack of these devices can jeopardise students' participation in online facilitation. This report is corroborated by Gillett-Swan (2017) who explains that lecturers and students in ODL require a wide range of resources including computers, webcam, power supply and stable internet connection and the absence of these resources could make simple instructional task like watching a video increasingly complex.

Conclusion

Online facilitation is a very suitable platform to promote classroom interaction between learners and facilitators. Without necessary coming together in a physical location. The results of the study yielded many significant insights about two central themes which are; nature of students' participation in online facilitation and challenges faced by them. Online facilitation is an innovation in technology to bridge the gap between distance learners and their facilitators. The study investigated the nature and extent of participation among learners as well as the factors constituting challenges to effective lesson delivery via online facilitation. This in turn provided data for informed recommendation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is therefore recommended that:

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1. ODL learners should be encouraged to participate in the various activities on the online facilitation platform provided by their institutions. A kind of incentive could be made available to those who are regular participants in the various activities highlighted such as accessing instructional videos, watching instructional videos, participating during the online live classes among others.
2. The ODL institutions should be better equipped in terms of regular supply of electricity as well as increased internet bandwidth to enhance learners' participation in those highlighted. Adequate electricity supply and broad internet bandwidth should form part of the core criteria for approval of ODL programmes in any institution.
3. The ODL administrators should go back to the drawing board to consider learners with family and work place constraints in expanding the flexibility on the programme to accommodate such. This could be in form of expanding facilities for virtual examination among others.
4. Companies should be encouraged to put at the fore, ODL institutions in the discharge of their social responsibilities to their host communities. This is due to the huge financial need for a functional ODL programmes and the level of yearning of Nigerians for education, which conventional system has not be able to meet.

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